

CEREAL CHAFF COLLECTION: PROJECT AGROINLOG RESULTS AND FIELD EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT: This work has been developed under the AGROinLOG Project, “*Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres for the Agro-industry sector in Europe*”. An Integrated Biomass Logistics Center (IBLC), is based on the introduction of new production chains into existing agro-industries by using new biomass feedstock. The AGROinLOG Project has dedicated great attention to investigate the potential of cereal chaff as a valuable resource. Chaff is the fine fraction of the threshing residues, not usually collected. Chaff is made up of glumes, seed husks, rachis and the tinner part of the cereal stems, whole and cracked kernels, as well as weed seeds. Currently there are several mechanical solutions available on the market for chaff recovery, and others are still at prototype stage, but they are not so common and very often unknown to the farmers. So far, the literature reports few cases of chaff collection with the specific purpose of weed seeds removal, but it still lacks specific experiments on these machines intentionally used for biomass collection. For this reason, during the Project AGROinLOG a series of large field tests were performed using an independent scientific approach with different kind of chaff harvesting technologies in France, Sweden and Italy from 2017 to 2019. The present study collects the results of these activities with the aim to fill that gap and provide deeper understanding in the possibility to enhance the current cereal harvesting method, in order to improve the quantity of biomass collected by including the chaff.

Keywords: threshing residues, combine harvester, straw baling, weed seeds, bioenergy

1 INTRODUCTION

AGROinLOG is a three-year Horizon 2020 Project, ended in 2020. The main goal of AGROinLOG Project has been the demonstration of the technical and economic feasibility of the *Integrated Biomass Logistics Centres* (IBLC) [1,2]. An IBLC is based on the introduction of new biomass feedstock into existing agroindustries to develop new business lines in their facilities to open new markets in bio-commodities and bio-products, such as second-generation bioethanol from cereal threshing residues. AGROinLOG Project dedicates great attention to investigate the potential of cereal chaff as a valuable resource.

Chaff is the fine fraction of the threshing residues collected by the sieves of the combine harvester during cereal threshing. Despite it represents a great amount of biomass (an availability of more than 50 Mt/year is assessed in Europe) and despite it is a valuable resource for energy or other industrial purposes or for animal feed and litter, it is usually not collected [3–7].

During the seed cleaning in the combine harvester, chaff retained by the sieves underneath the straw walkers is blown to the rear of the combine. Usually, this material is simply left to fall on the ground and covered by the straw. The layer in direct contact with the ground cannot be collected with the pick-up in the following baling operation.

The growing interest in the exploitation of these residues both for energy purposes and for husbandry uses has pushed some constructors to develop systems for the recovery of the chaff. Moreover, in organic farming the interest comes from the reduction of the weed seed stock in the soil by removing weed seeds before they are returned to the field [8,9].

Currently, several solutions for chaff harvesting are available on the market, and other are still at prototype stage. Conceptually, they are based on two management methods: the collection of chaff together with straw; the collection of chaff separately from straw. In the first case,

chaff is discharged either on top or inside of the straw swath and then it is baled together with the straw. In the separate collection method, the chaff is delivered to dedicated collection systems, such as trailers towed by a tractor or by the combine itself, or integrated containers in the combine, or non-stop balers [10].

The chaff harvesting technologies are not so common and very often unknown to the farmers. The spread of these technologies could therefore favour the development of new markets.

So far, the literature reports few cases of chaff collection with the specific purpose of weed seeds removal, but it still lacks specific experiments on these machines intentionally used for biomass collection.

For this reason, during the Project AGROinLOG a series of large field tests were performed using an independent scientific approach with different kind of chaff harvesting technologies in France, Sweden and Italy from 2017 to 2019 [11–14].

The present study aimed to fill that gap and provide deeper understanding in the possibility to enhance the current cereal harvesting method, in order to improve the quantity of biomass collected by including the chaff.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Harvesting test using Thievin technology in France

The tests were carried out during wheat grain harvesting in July 2018 and July 2019. The two-year tests were carried out both on the same field, in Le Flux (Pannecè, France) (47°29'16.4"N 1°13'26.1"W).

The turbine system for chaff recovery developed by the French manufacturer, named “Turbopaille”, consists of a hopper placed in the rear part of the combine harvester that collects the chaff exiting from the combine. A horizontal auger inside the hopper transports the material to the hydraulically driven turbine that generates the cyclone for the expulsion of the material (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Thievin system “Turbopaille” for chaff collection

During the test, three different arrangements were compared (treatments) (Figure 2):

- discharging of the chaff over the straw swath for baling of the straw and chaff together (Treatment A);
- convey the chaff on a trailer towed by a tractor moving in a lateral side, through the application of PVC pipe (Treatment B, tested only in 2019)
- spreading of the chaff by applying a “V” shaped spreader (Treatment C);

Figure 2: Thievin system working arrangements: unloading of the chaff on the straw swath (A); unloading of the chaff on a trailer (B); chaff spreading (C)

2.2 Harvesting test using Thierart technology in Sweden

The tests were carried out by CREA in collaboration with the Research Institutes of Sweden AB -RISE at Lilla Boslin (Halland region, Sweden) in 2019.

The device named “double-stage turbine” developed by the French company Thierart was installed

at the end of the cleaning shoe of the combine harvester. As shown in Figure 3, the device is made of a tank that receives the chaff from the cleaning shoe; within it, there is a steel-made screw that delivers the chaff to the two-stage turbine which, in turn, blows it through the outlet.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the Thierart system for chaff collection

Here, a PVC pipe is connected, to permit the discharge of the chaff, either on the swath (Figure 4A) or onto a 6 m³ trailer (Figure 4B). The screw and the twin-stage turbine are driven by the dedicated hydraulic system.

Figure 4: Thierart system working arrangements: unloading of the chaff on the straw swath (A); unloading of the chaff on a trailer towed by the combine harvester (B)

Both residue collection systems were compared (treatments):

- chaff blown over the swath of straw for a simultaneous baling of the straw and chaff. (Treatment A)
- chaff discharged in a trailer towed by the combine harvester and the straw in a swath for a separated collection of the straw and chaff. (Treatment B).

2.3 Harvesting test using Rekordverken technology in Sweden.

In August 2017 and August 2019, two winter wheat residues harvesting tests were carried out using combine harvesters equipped with Rekordverken Combi System in Sweden.

The study was conducted first in August 2017 near Vattholma (Uppsala region, SE) (60°00'54.0"N 17°39'19.1"E). The wheat residue harvesting test was carried out using a hybrid combine harvester (Hybrid Fendt 9490) equipped with Rekordverken Combi System (RCS). The hybrid combine has a threshing system based on an axial separation system with two separation rotors that provide a more efficient seeds separation in comparison to the straw-walker system. On the other hand, the hybrid system mistreats the straw more strongly by reducing its length and thus making it more difficult for the baler to collect the straw.

A second test was carried out in August 2019 near Alunda (Uppsala region, SE) (60°05'29.7"N 18°07'04.7"E). Due to a high loss recorded during the first harvesting experience mainly caused by the use of a hybrid combine, in this second test a traditional combine with straw walkers was used.

The combine (New Holland CX5.80) used during the second test in 2019 had a threshing system based a rotary separator, and an additional straw-flow beater downstream of the cross separator rotor, that can be turned off for a less intense threshing effect and consequently also a longer straw.

The Combi system developed by the Swedish machine manufacturer Rekordverken distributes the straw and chaff separately or handle them together. It is made possible since the chaff spreader can be regulated to throw the material to the sides or to the back into the straw chopper (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The Combi system developed by the Swedish machine manufacturer Rekordverken (source: <http://www.rekordverken.se>).

During the tests in 2017 and 2019, two treatments were tested (Figure 6):

- Rekordverken in Spreading mode: The chaff is thrown laterally to the device. The straw is collected in a windrow (Treatment C).
- Rekordverken in Admixing mode: The chaff is directed into the straw and windrowed together with it (Treatment D).

Figure 6: Rekordverken system working arrangements: spreading of the chaff (treatment C); admixing the chaff inside the straw swath (treatment D)

2.4 Harvesting test using the “Harcob” system developed the company Agricinque of Racca in Italy

The study was conducted in July 2019 in the Northern Italy at Savigliano (44.627482 N, 7.698242 E), Cuneo province. The test was performed during wheat grain harvesting carried out with a combine harvester machine, model Axial Flow 7140, equipped with the “Harcob” system developed by the company Agricinque of Racca (Figure 7).

The system was developed for the simultaneous harvesting of maize grain and maize cobs in an additional tank of 9 m³. It was modified in order to collect wheat chaff, changing the sieves according to the dimension of the wheat seeds and the crushing elements (knife) of the beating cylinder.

The “Harcob” system allows to perform in a single-pass grain and chaff harvesting with simultaneous unloading of the products (grain and chaff) in two different trailers.

Figure 7: The Harcob system developed by the Italian manufacturer Agricinque di Racca modified for the simultaneous harvesting of wheat seeds and chaff

2.5 Experimental protocol

Every field test was performed following the same experimental protocol.

Before harvesting the field test was divided in three

blocks of the same surface in order to have three replicates for each treatment.

The potential biomass availability in terms of straw, stubbles, seeds and chaff was evaluated, in 10 sample areas of 1 m² each randomly chosen. Plants of each sample area were kept separated (straw from the ears) and weighed directly in field using a precision scale, and the wheat ears of each sample area were bagged and shipped to CREA institute in order to determine the single fractions (chaff and seeds) using a laboratory thresher.

The harvesting tests concerned the threshing and the baling steps performed in each experimental unit (plot). Machines performance (working times and fuel consumption), yield, moisture content and bulk density of biomass, were the parameters measured. Moreover, after harvesting, the average cutting height and the losses were assessed.

Working time study was performed according to ASAE standard. Fuel consumption of each machine involved (combine, baler and tractor) was determined through tank refilling until full level at the end of each plot.

Biomass yield was obtained weighing at the farm scale the seed, the chaff and the straw harvested, and relating their weight to surface of each plot. Three sample of threshing residues before baling, chaff and seeds were taken to determine their moisture content. For seeds and chaff the bulk density was assessed according to the technical standard. The bulk density of bales was estimated by weighing 5 single bales for each treatment and relating the weight to their volume.

The average cutting height was assessed by measuring 100 random cutting heights. The biomass left on the ground as stubble was assessed by weighing 30 bunches of 10 stacks of wheat. Then they were cut from the base to a length equal to the cutting height, and the cut part was weighed.

Seed, chaff and straw losses were assessed as difference between the potential amount of biomass (estimated with the pre-harvest plots) and the amount harvested.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Harvesting straw and wheat chaff using Thievin technology.

The total biomass estimated in 2019 pre-harvest measurements was about 1.9 t/ha higher than 2018 (16.8 t/ha). The wheat ears were in both years 44% the total biomass (56% straw), with the same repartition in the ears of seeds (about 78 %) and chaff (22 %).

The combine performances were not influenced by the working arrangements, not even when the combine and the trailer towed by the tractor had to work side by side (in 2019 test).

The effective field capacity of two years tests was on average 2.14 ha/h (Table I). The fuel consumption, measured only in 2019, was on average 21.63 l/ha (46.7 l/h), with no significant differences among treatments.

Table I: Effective field capacity of the combine harvester equipped with the Thievin system in 2018 and 2019 according to the treatments

Treatment	Effective Field Capacity (ha/h)	
	2018	2019
A(on swath)	2.24±0.11	1.98±0.02
B(on Trailer)	Not performed	2.03±0.11
C(spreading)	2.41±0.10	2.04±0.06

Considering the baling operation, statistically significant differences were found for what concern the effective field capacity (ha h⁻¹) between A and C mode (Table II). Baling the swaths that contained more biomass (A mode: straw + chaff) was significantly slower than baling the swaths with less biomass (C mode: only straw).

In 2019, the fuel consumption during the baling for treatment A (6.21 l/ha, 19.13 l/h) was about double respect to the other treatments.

Table II: Baler performance in 2018 and 2019 according to treatments (values marked with asterisks within 2018 columns are significantly different (p<0.05); common letters within 2019 columns denote the absence of significant difference (p<0.05))

Treatment	Effective Field Capacity (ha/h)	
	2018	2019
A(on swath)	3.46±0.28(*)	3.09±0.13(b)
B(on Trailer)	Not performed	3.33±0.09(ab)
C(spreading)	4.05±0.16(*)	3.45±0.10(a)

The biomass baled in treatment A (straw + chaff) was in both years statistically higher than biomass baled in treatment C (only straw) (Figure 8).

The difference between biomass baled in the two treatments allowed to assess the chaff baled, respectively 1.39 t/ha in 2018 and 2.19 t/ha in 2019.

With the discharging on the trailer (2019), 1.27 t/ha of chaff was collected, about 0.9 t/ha less than chaff discharged on the swath and baled with straw.

Figure 8: Quantity of biomass harvested in 2018 and 2019 with Thievin system according to the treatments (common letters denote the absence of significant difference ($p < 0.05$))

3.2 Harvesting straw and wheat chaff using Thierart technology.

The total biomass was assessed equal to 18,8 t/ha. The ears were the 57 % (47 % seeds and 10 % chaff) and the straw was the 43 % of the total biomass in the field.

Unlike harvesting experiences in France where the wheat chaff was unloaded onto a tractor-driven trailer, in Sweden's residue harvesting tests with Thierart device, the treatment that provided the chaff was unloaded onto a trailer towed directly from the combine showed statistically significant differences in effective field capacity during combine harvesting (Table III). In fact, due to the need to unload the trailer (of just 6 m³) several times during harvesting, the unproductive times of the combine were 233 % higher than the thesis in which the combine unloaded the chaff directly over the windrow.

Considering the baling operation, the effective field capacity (that includes accessories times, such as turning time and unloading time) of treatment A (chaff on swath) were significantly higher than treatment B (chaff on trailer). Baling the swaths that contained more biomass (straw and chaff) was significantly slower than baling the swaths with less biomass (only straw) as observed during the test in France.

Table III: Combine and baler performance according to treatments.

Treatment	Effective Field Capacity(ha/h)	
	Harvesting	Baling
A(on swath)	1.71±0.36 (a)	1.57±0.15 (d)
B(on trailer)	1.02±0.18 (b)	1.92±0.09 (c)

Either the chaff baled with the straw and the chaff collected separately onto the trailer were about 0,8 t/ha (Figure 9).

Both the chaff and straw collected were about 50% lower than the theoretical amount estimated from the pre-harvest tests. This was due to the narrow pick-up of the round baler that caused high loss of residue along the swath.

Figure 9: Biomass potential estimated in pre-harvest and biomass harvested (chaff and straw) according to the treatments with Thierart technology in Sweden.

3.3 Harvesting straw and wheat chaff using Rekorderverken technology in Sweden.

The total biomass of the wheat field in 2017 and 2019 was 13.5 and 19.4 t_{dm}/ha, respectively. The spikes represented the 63 % of the total biomass in the 2017 and 57 % in the 2019. In both years grain harvesting, and straw baling were not affected by the treatments (Table IV and Table V).

Table IV: Combine performance in 2017 and 2019 according to treatments.

Treatment	Effective Field Capacity(ha/h)	
	2017	2019
C (spreading)	3.1±0.3	1.47±0.04
D (admixing)	3.2±0.3	1.44±0.03

Table V: Baler performance in 2017 and 2019 according to treatments

Treatment	Effective Field Capacity(ha/h)	
	2017	2019
C (spreading)	1.57±0.21	2.37±0.1
D (admixing)	1.73±0.55	2.32±0.19

The system Rekordverken allowed the collection of additional biomass by incorporating the chaff in the straw during the discharging by the combine. In fact, during the test, Rekordverken in admixing mode permitted to collect 336 kg/ha of fresh matter more than the spreading of the chaff (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Biomass potential estimated in pre-harvest and biomass harvested (chaff and straw) in 2019 with Rekordverken system

3.4 Harvesting straw and wheat chaff using Harcob technology

Results of pre-harvesting test highlighted 25.9 tons of total biomass per hectare, of which 11.5 tons of seeds and 2.48 of chaff. The amount of straw was estimated in 8.58.

The value of effective field capacity and fuel consumption (1.19 ha/h and 29.86 l/h, respectively) were similar to the results recorded during maize cob harvesting.

Wheat harvesting by using this innovative machine highlighted a yield of 0.67 t/ha for chaff (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Biomass potential estimated in pre-harvest and biomass harvested (chaff and straw) in 2019 with Harcob System

The cleaning and separation devices of the combine harvester were not able to separate the chaff from the straw. The result was that 10 % of straw was inside the tank of the chaff and that the windrow discharged by the machine was made by 50 % of chaff and 50 % of straw.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Chaff represents a great amount of the total wheat residues. The effective quantity of chaff harvested depends not only on the harvesting technology used, but on the whole harvesting system: the working arrangement, the type and settings of the combine harvesters and balers, the residues handling mode.

The choice of the collection system should consider

the final use of the chaff. Chaff collected with straw is mainly valuable for energy purposes, while the separate collection would allow a wider range of possible uses of chaff and straw.

Aftermarket devices that provide for the collection of chaff together with straw have a limited investment cost, are easily adaptable to all types of combine harvester and they don't influence the harvesting performance.

On the other hand, the collection of loose chaff separately from straw has higher costs and it could be preferred in the presence of a dedicated market for chaff or in the case of organic farming (removing the weed seeds).

In fact, although in Europe weed seed removal is not the main purpose of chaff collection, it is a valid strategy for weed control as demonstrated by the Australian "Harvest Weed Seed Control" (HWSC) strategies.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Gómez, M.; Zapata, S.; Izquierdo, M.; Jarauta-Córdoba, C.; Annevelink, E.; Snels, J.; Urciuoli, L.; Kougioumtzis, M.A.; Karampinis, E.; Grammelis, P.; et al. From agroindustries to integrated biomass logistics centres. Agroinlog project: Summary of final results. In Proceedings of the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition Proceedings; ETA-Florence Renewable Energies, 2020; pp. 941–952.
- [2] Annevelink, B.; Van Gogh, B.; Nogués, F.S.; Espatolero, S.; De La Cruz, T.; Luzzini, D.; Karampinis, M.; Kougioumtzis, M.; Olsson, J. Conceptual description of an integrated biomass logistics centre (IBLC). In Proceedings of the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition Proceedings; ETA-Florence Renewable Energies, 2017; Vol. 2017, pp. 200–203.
- [3] McCartney, D.H.; Block, H.C.; Dubeski, P.L.; Ohama, A.J. Review: The composition and availability of straw and chaff from small grain cereals for beef cattle in western Canada. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 2006, 86, 443–455.
- [4] Rönnbäck, M.; Lundin, G. Simultaneous Harvesting of Straw and Chaff for Energy Purposes-Influence on Bale Density, Yield, Field Drying Process and Combustion Characteristics. In Proceedings of the XVIIth World Congress of the International Commission of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering (CIGR) Hosted by the Canadian Society for Bioengineering (CSBE/SCGAB) Québec City, Canada June 13-17, 2010; 2010.
- [5] Mann, M.E.; Cohen, R.D.H.; Kernan, J.A.; Nicholson, H.H.; Christensen, D.A.; Smart, M.E. The feeding value of ammoniated flax straw, wheat straw and wheat chaff for beef cattle. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 1988.
- [6] Gerling, M.; Dickey, P.C. Patent N 5878696. Absorbant animal bedding 1999, 8.
- [7] Pari, L.; Toscano, G.; Suardi, A.; Bergonzoli, S.; Lopez, E.; Scarfone, A.; Alfano, V. Maize cob and cereal chaff: Feedstocks for energy production. In Proceedings of the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition Proceedings; ETA-Florence Renewable Energies, 2018; Vol. 2018, pp. 279–282.
- [8] Walsh, M.; Newman, P.; Powles, S. Targeting Weed Seeds In-Crop: A New Weed Control Paradigm for Global Agriculture. *Weed Technol.* 2013.

- [9] Walsh, M.J.; Harrington, R.B.; Powles, S.B. Harrington Seed Destructor: A new nonchemical weed control tool for global grain crops. *Crop Sci.* 2012.
- [10] Pari, L.; Alfano, V.; Scarfone, A.; Bergonzoli, S.; Suardi, A.; Lazar, S. Best available technologies to harvest cereal chaff. In *Proceedings of the European Biomass Conference and Exhibition Proceedings*; 2018.
- [11] Suardi, A.; Stefanoni, W.; Alfano, V.; Bergonzoli, S.; Pari, L. Equipping a combine harvester with turbine technology increases the recovery of residual biomass from cereal crops via the collection of chaff. *Energies* 2020, 13.
- [12] Suardi, A.; Stefanoni, W.; Bergonzoli, S.; Latterini, F.; Jonsson, N.; Pari, L. Comparison between two strategies for the collection of wheat residue after mechanical harvesting: Performance and cost analysis. *Sustain.* 2020, 12.
- [13] Suardi, A.; Saia, S.; Stefanoni, W.; Gunnarsson, C.; Sundberg, M.; Pari, L. Admixing chaff with straw increased the residues collected without compromising machinery efficiencies. *Energies* 2020, 13.
- [14] Bergonzoli, S.; Suardi, A.; Rezaie, N.; Alfano, V.; Pari, L. An innovative system for Maize Cob and wheat chaff harvesting: Simultaneous grain and residues collection. *Energies* 2020, 13.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was performed in the framework of the European project AGROinLOG “Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres for the Agro-industry sector in Europe”.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 727961.

7 LOGO SPACE

